

PERCEPTION OF SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF GENDER EQUITY AND THEIR ATTITUDE TOWARDS GENDER ROLE

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Perception of Saint Mary's University Senior High School Students of Gender Equity and Their Attitude towards Gender Role

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Abstract

Due to the current state of gender inequality, it is typical for both boys and girls to experience physical, sexual, or psychological harm based solely on their sex in both public and educational settings. This study aims to determine the students of Saint Mary's University Senior High School (SMU SHS) of their perception of gender equity. Additionally, this study seeks to determine the attitudes toward gender roles. The researchers used both qualitative and quantitative design and determined its research locale in Saint Mary's University Senior High School, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, and the SMU SHS student population, both Grade 11 and Grade 12 as research participants. Furthermore, the researchers made use of Stratified Random Sampling as the sampling method used in the Senior High School Department. The study used a mixed-method design and used various statistical tools to analyze data specifically, thematic analysis for qualitative data and inferential statistics. Results have shown that the respondents have a positive perception of gender equity, while a negative attitude toward gender roles. For the perception of the respondents towards gender equity when they were grouped according to their profile variable there is a significant difference in their perception, except for family type. For attitudes toward gender roles, there is a significant difference in attitude. Lastly, for relationships, there is a high positive correlation between a respondent's perception of gender equity and their attitudes towards gender roles. These findings may imply the urgency of promoting gender equity awareness and challenging restrictive gender roles in education. The findings also emphasize the need for proactive engagement with religious communities to foster a more inclusive understanding of gender, advocating for a delicate balance in restricting students' freedom while promoting awareness through educational initiatives and online promotion to create a more inclusive school culture help understand the influence of religious sects on respondents' attitudes towards gender roles and the administration of the school should advocate restricting students' freedom to express themselves, promoting awareness about gender roles and their negative impact, and highlighting the importance of inclusivity through online promotion and advertisement.

Keywords: *gender, gender equity, gender roles, perception of gender equity, attitude towards gender roles*

Introduction

Gender equity and roles have been a subject of discussion and debate for decades. It refers to the equal treatment of all individuals, regardless of gender, in all aspects of life. Perceptions of gender equity and attitudes toward gender roles are essential in shaping society's perceptions and beliefs about gender and the roles individuals should play based on their gender. The researchers are interested in assessing students' understanding of attitudes toward gender roles, and the promotion of gender equality has received top priority according to student gender attitudes in various nations. Because of the current state of gender inequality, it is typical for both boys and girls to experience physical, sexual, or psychological harm based solely on their gender in both public and educational settings. Consequently, it is critical to assess students' gender role attitudes and perceptions of gender equality concerning moral values and ideas about equal capacity. Gender role attitudes are a person's beliefs that mirror their perspectives on the roles of men and women in society. These attitudes encompass an individual's convictions regarding the societal roles that men and women should undertake.

Gender equity and roles do not exist in isolation; instead, they intertwine with other social identities such as race, ethnicity, socioeconomic status, and religion. This study compares the perception of senior high school students toward gender equity and their attitudes toward gender roles. This comparison can reveal any gender disparities, biases, or perspective differences that may exist within the environment of Saint Mary's University

(SMU). This study would also have been the first to conduct a study about gender equity and gender roles at SMU, specifically in the Senior High School. Additionally, this study is up to date with other studies regarding the students' perception of gender equity and attitudes toward gender roles.

Gender Equity

Gender equity differs from gender equality. Gender equity can be thought of as the method used to attain gender equality. Gender equity entails treating everyone equally and without prejudice, regardless of gender. It also entails resolving gender disparities that, depending on a person's gender, restrict their access to possibilities for improved health, education, and economic opportunity (Martinez, 2022). Gender equity is crucial because historically, societies all over the world have viewed women, transgender people,

and nonbinary people as "weaker" or less significant than males. Additionally, gender equity is the provision of fairness and justice in the distribution of benefits and responsibilities between women, men, and all genders.

Research about gender equity has shown that attitudes towards gender roles can vary depending on various factors such as culture, education, and upbringing. The study has found that traditional gender roles are still prevalent in many societies, leading to gender-based discrimination and unequal opportunities. For example, a study on Pakistani University students found that traditional gender roles were deeply ingrained in society and that men were expected to be the breadwinners while women were expected to be homemakers (Ahmad & Khan, 2019).

Though people understand the concept of gender equity, there are various circumstances wherein students as well as teachers and staff do not understand gender-based discrimination or violence that hinders the promotion of gender equity. A study by Ashford et al. (2020) found that although Australian high school students supported gender equity, there were still significant gaps in their understanding of gender-based discrimination and how to challenge gender stereotypes.

In another study on gender equity, researchers conducted a comparative analysis between India and Sweden to assess the levels of gender equity among male and female students at Patrician and Gavle University. The findings indicated that both universities exhibited evidence, for instance the parental leave policies and the gender wage gap, of gender equity; however, the study emphasized a need for improvement (Janoris & Prela, 2019).

With the promotion of gender equity in school, there are major influences that students gain from their household that affects their perceptions of the promotion of gender equity. In a study by Dahal et al. (2022), the subjugation or violence that most women experience in Nepal was gender-based violence, due to gender differences, constricted life opportunities, and internalization of constructed differences among women.

With gender-based violence affecting the daily life of not only women but also men, a study that focused on the situation of hate crimes in gender and sexuality-based discrimination in Spain, showed that there are citizens in Spain who experience violence, based on the grounds of sexual orientation, gender identity, and gender expression. Though there were no reports of gender-based violence in Equality Commissions in the six Spanish universities (Nieto et al., 2021).

As gender-based violence affects the promotion of gender equity, various variables hinder its promotion such as gender discrimination. A study aimed to determine the extent to which Romanian perspectives or current education practitioners are informed about gender discrimination problems, to infer whether they are prepared to promote gender equality within the school (Popa et al., 2014). In Romania where being born as a girl is considered a disadvantage, results have shown that women experience the most gender discrimination.

With the issue of the increasing gender inequality in schools, the researchers discussed the possible effects on religious groups or political institutions on gender equality. One example is the investigation of whether political institutions, culture, and religious groups underlie gender inequality in education. Results have shown that political institutions do not significantly influence the education of girls: autocratic regimes do not discriminate against girls in denying educational opportunities and democracies do not discriminate by gender when providing educational opportunities. The primary influence on gender equity in education is culture and religion (Cooray & Potrafke, 2011).

Perception of Gender Equity

A person's perception of gender equity can be varied from different external factors like culture or the environment itself. Most societies have a patriarchal society - a system of controlling women through economic dependence, violence, and domestication. Where males are directed to support the public sphere of work and decision-making (Cataldi & Reardon 1996). Thus, such system hinders gender equity and its promotion in every society with patriarchal origin.

Gender inequity is not only experienced in Western countries, nor countries with a specific religion. According to Adamson (2007), Gender equity has become a debate in public spheres and academic forums as well as a crucial issue in Indonesia.

Various studies showed different perceptions about gender equity depending on their sex. There are some circumstances where women have set ideals due to the sense that men should lead. A study by Zdravkovic et al., (2020) has shown that both men and women have perceived that their gender can become a disadvantage when competing in department leadership. Results have shown that women aspired less to take leadership positions than men and have reported that women have been mistreated at clinical work.

A study entitled, "The Perception of Gender Equity: A Case of Iraq". This study sought to determine if women in higher education are at a disadvantage in terms of career progression, interaction with students, and inclusion in administrative roles and decision-making. The study showed that career progression is higher in men than women. This shows that men have a higher advantage in career progression than women in Iraq (Jaber, 1970).

According to a study by Henderson et al. (2022), gender equity is widely recognized to be an important driver of successful organizations. In this study, when referring to gender equity, the researchers adopted the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) definition: fairness of treatment for women and men, according to their respective needs. This may

include equal treatment or treatment that is different which is considered equivalent in terms of rights, benefits, obligations and opportunities. That being the case, gender equity markers of achievement should be complemented with broader aspects of equality, diversity, and inclusion.

According to Mustofa (2021), gender equity has been covered by many communities of society including the government. It is supposed to include gender equity material in the curriculum so that stakeholders and all school elements have awareness and are proactive in promoting gender equity in education. In this study's discussion, it was stated that men are more appropriate and suitable to lead than women because they are more assertive and authoritative, women are usually too carried away, and they are also busy with household matters so that time is not effective at school.

Gender Roles

Gender roles can be cultural and personal, it determines how males and females should think, speak, dress, and interact within a society. These roles are social constructs developed over time and are not based on human behavior; this is because gender roles evolved as a way to organize the necessary tasks done in early human society. In society, gender roles refer to how we are expected to behave, speak, dress, groom, and carry ourselves according to the sex to which we have been assigned. For instance, girls and women are frequently expected to behave politely, be accommodating, and be nurturing; while males are typically supposed to be powerful, combative, and brave. Some say that because traditional gender roles have been done or practiced. Gender is one of such factors also mentioned in the literature to have considerable effects on students' academic performances especially in science subjects. Gender is the range of physical, biological, mental, and behavioral characteristics pertaining to and differentiating between the feminine and masculine population (Adigun, 2015).

According to Gabato et al. (2022), examining the gender roles of Philippine State University officials in the implementation of Gender and Development programs becomes essential in understanding how societal norms influence perceptions and expectations. The term "gender roles" refers to societal expectations dictating how men and women should behave, think, and perform tasks, shaping individuals' actions based on imposed norms. These roles are established early in life and are influenced by family, education, peer groups, and media. Unfortunately, repeated interactions within these agents can perpetuate stereotypes, leading to perceived differences between genders and reinforcing inequalities. It is crucial to distinguish gender roles from sex roles, as the former are societal constructs, while the latter are biological roles. Investigating how these dynamics manifest among officials at Philippine State University provides valuable insights into the intersection of institutional practices and gender expectations, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of gender roles in the context of development programs.

A study by Alcantara (1994) revealed that husband and wife are appointed as the domestic manager and the head of the household, respectively, in traditional patriarchal civilizations. The husband is recognized as the head of the household and is therefore expected to care for the family financially, even if Filipino households are not rigidly structured according to patriarchal ideologies. On the other hand, the wife's primary tasks are managing the family money, raising children, and providing for them and her husband.

According to Leaper and Bigler (2011), gender is a central aspect of identity throughout the life course and across cultures, and gender identity has been a topic of consistent interest to gender development researchers.

A study from Pennsylvania State University states that many gender roles are determined by a society's requirements and the environment. The article "The Social Construction of Gender" also discusses how ethnicity, a society's historical and cultural heritage, and gender norms all differ from one another. For instance, many ancient Native American and African tribes had matriarchal societies, which meant that women frequently served as leaders, healers, and other significant figures in their communities. In contrast to other Asian and European countries, where men held all social and political power, this one does not. Therefore, gender roles vary greatly depending on the time or place. It is apparent that in the current era, these typecasts based on sex are of no actual value to human civilization as a whole because they were made up and can alter depending on the context in which they are utilized. Because they are inconsistent and unreliable, they should not be used as a standard for how members of a particular sex should behave (Hernandez, 2006).

In recent decades, the differences in achievement for male and female students have been the topic of much discussion and research. It is a common belief that students perceive each gender to have normative traits that equate to certain levels of success in school; the prolonged reproduction of these sets of standards forms gender stereotypes (Vernier & Martinot, 2015).

Another study with gender roles is that it is mainly used conventionally to describe how society gives certain roles to boys and girls. Gender has to do with behaviors that have become associated with masculinity and femininity, and with how people see their roles as male or female (Kauffman, 1997). Therefore, gender is related to how individuals perceive themselves in such a way that most people of the same sex identify themselves with certain attributes.

Gender roles are socially ascribed duties, responsibilities, and functions based on the notion of maleness and femaleness. It is a broad term that encompasses all socially ascribed expectations for boys and girls. It includes such arrangements that portray men as the heads of household and occupants of the public, while women have to be housewives, to care for their husbands and children, and to respect privacy (Blackstone, 2017).

High school students perceived the professions of district governor (public administration), military officer, policeman, engineer, judge, prosecutor, and architect as predominantly male occupations. On the other hand, students perceived the professions of nurse and dietician as mainly female occupations. The study findings demonstrated that high school students classify various professions as strictly male or female professions. These results demonstrated the significance of school psychological counselors who provide counseling services to students during the career selection process to raise awareness of the students by organizing group guidance activities on gender role perceptions and possible outcomes of various professions (Atli, 2017).

Attitude toward Gender Roles

Attitudes toward gender equity and gender roles can vary widely depending on cultural, social, and political contexts. Some people believe that men and women should have equal opportunities and rights and that gender should not determine one's roles or abilities. Others may hold more traditional views about gender, such as believing that men should be the primary breadwinners and women should be responsible for domestic and caregiving tasks.

In recent years, there has been a growing awareness of the negative impact of rigid gender roles and the importance of promoting gender equity. Research has shown that gender equity can have a positive impact on individuals, families, and communities, including improved health outcomes, economic stability, and social cohesion. As such, it is crucial to continue exploring attitudes towards gender equity and gender roles to create a more equitable and just society for all individuals.

Another study states that currently, due to gender-based inequality, gender-related violence including sexual, physical, or psychological harm to girls and boys based on their sex is common in the classroom as well as public domain (Sultana et al. 2015). Therefore, it is important to measure the student's gender role attitudes towards equity on the particular aspect of equal ability beliefs and moral values. Attitudes of gender roles refer to someone's attitudes that reflect beliefs about the roles of men and women. These are influenced by many aspects of social and cultural stereotypes. It is commonly believed that gender roles can be learned to perform the appropriate role towards family, society, community, or other social groups. The study attempts to measure the student's gender role attitudes towards equality on ability, beliefs, and moral values aspects in a total of 300 students from two higher learning institutions in Malaysia. Self-administered semi-structured questionnaires were handed to each respondent and the information was collected directly by the researchers.

Another study examines gender role attitudes among university students in Partium, a region on the border of Romania & Hungary (Fényes, 2014). The study involved 295 students from various fields of study and found that traditional views on gender roles were prevalent among the majority of participants, with women being expected to fulfill domestic duties and men being responsible for providing financial support. The study suggests that these attitudes may be influenced by cultural and historical factors in the region and calls for further research to better understand gender attitudes in the area and to promote gender equality.

According to the study by Cahill & Adams (1997), the study explored the attitude of teachers in early childhood about their attitudes in gender role behavior. The study resulted in showing that early childhood teachers express some openness to children exploring gender roles, and feel more comfortable with girls, rather than boys, exploring male and female gender roles. The study shows that teachers are more in favor of girls than boys.

This study is motivated by the increasing attention paid to gender equity and the need to address gender-based discrimination, particularly in educational institutions. The research paper explores how students perceive and understand gender equity, and their attitude toward gender roles, and their willingness to challenge gender stereotypes and norms. In the context of Saint Mary's University Senior High School (SMUSHS) in terms of gender issues, an example was during the United Nations (UN) Month celebration last 2022, the researchers examined that students from different strands have various ideologies that the traditional clothing of the Philippines which was the Filipinina, it was said to be for girls only when a member of the LGBT+ community wore the said traditional clothing. Additionally, when students stereotype that certain colors are for girls and women only and not for the opposite genders, which shows a negative ideology of assigning colors to specific gender. This shows a certain exclusivity and discrimination against other students of SMUSHS.

This research paper aims to explore the perception of senior high school students from Saint Mary's University toward gender equity, their attitudes towards gender roles, and respondents' recommendations on how to promote gender equity inside SMUSHS. The findings of this research paper contribute to the existing literature on attitudes toward gender equity and roles and provide insights into how educational institutions can foster gender equity and promote inclusive attitudes toward gender. It is hoped that the results of this study encourage further research and action toward achieving gender equity in our society.

Research Questions

This research paper aims to explore the perception of senior high school students from Saint Mary's University toward gender equity. Additionally, this study will determine the students' attitudes toward gender roles that hinder the promotion of gender equity, as well as the respondents recommendation on the promotion of gender equity in the school. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the perceptions of the respondent toward gender equity?

2. What are the attitudes of the respondents toward gender roles?
3. Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents towards gender equity when grouped according:
 - 3.1 gender;
 - 3.2 track or strand; and
 - 3.3 family type?
4. Is there a significant difference in the attitude of the respondents toward gender roles when grouped according to:
 - 4.1 gender;
 - 4.2 track or strand; and
 - 4.3 family type?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the attitude of the respondents toward gender roles and their perception of gender equity?
6. What are the respondents’ recommendations to promote gender equity (respecting all people without discrimination, regardless of their gender) in school?

Methodology

In this section, the methods used to complete the presented study. Specifically, this chapter involves the study’s research design, locale, respondents, research instruments, data gathering procedure, treatment of data, and ethical considerations.

Research Design

This study has used quantitative and qualitative research, specifically descriptive-comparative design because it involves measuring the variables. In Layman’s terms, the study deals with statistics and numbers. Additionally, the descriptive-comparative design was utilized to analyze which gender has a better positive attitude in terms of gender roles and perception of gender equity and which strand has a better positive perception of gender equity and negative attitude in terms of gender roles. Moreover, it analyzed if the students’ family type highly affects how they have a better perception of gender equity and attitude in terms of gender roles.

Along with the descriptive-comparative design, this study uses the descriptive- correlational design to determine if there is a significant relationship between the perceptions of the respondents regarding gender equity and their attitudes towards gender roles when they are grouped according to their profile variable.

On the contrary, the study also used qualitative research design to be conscious of the students’ opinions concerning the question: What are your recommendations on the promotion of Gender Equity (respecting all people without discrimination, regardless of their gender) in school?

Participants

The research participants were Grade 11 and 12 students from all strands of SMU SHS. The researchers used stratified random sampling as a sampling method for their study, to equally distribute the questionnaire to different subgroups. There are three strands in the academic tracks, with three sections of the ABM Strand, four in the HUMSS Strand, and eighteen sections in the STEM. For the TVL track with two strands. There are two in the TVL- ICT Strand and two in the TVL-HE Strand. Two sections for the AD Strand, the total population of both the Grade 11 and 12 students in Saint Mary’s University Senior High School is 1,049.

To determine the sample size for the study, the researchers used the Solvin Formula. The formula is written as; $n = \frac{N}{1 + \frac{N}{Ne}}$. Where n = Sample Size, N = Population Size, and e = Margin of Error. Hence the formula is substituted as:

$$n = \frac{1,049}{1 + 1,049 (0.05)^2}$$

The total number of students in the STEM Strand is 744, while HUMSS Strand is 138, and ABM is 95. For the Technological Vocational Livelihood (TVL) track, the total population of the TVL-HE strand is 25, TVL-ICT is 26, and Arts and Design (AD) is 21. The overall population of the Technological Vocational Livelihood (TVL) track is 72 since each strand in the TVL Track has two sections per strand. The research questionnaires were distributed to 290 respondents.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage of research participants in each section*

Factor	Group	n	%
Gender	Male	79	27.2%
	Female	159	54.8%
	Lesbian	5	1.7%
	Gay	8	2.8%
	Bisexual	27	9.3%
	Pansexual	10	3.4%

Strand	Non-Binary	2	.7%
	TVL-ICT	26	9.0%
	HUMSS	39	13.4%
	TVL-HE	20	6.9%
	STEM	164	56.6%
	ABM	20	6.9%
	AD	21	7.2%
Family Type	Nuclear Family	178	61.4%
	Single-Parent Family	44	15.2%
	Extended Family	37	12.8%
	Stepfamily	13	4.5%
	Grand Parent Family	18	6.2%
	Total	290	100.0%

Table 1 shows the frequency count and percentage of the respondents when they are grouped according to gender, strand, and family type. The results implied that the majority of people who answered the questionnaire were female students, followed by male students from different grade levels and strands. Meanwhile, respondents of the STEM strand with 56.6% of the sample population which is followed by the HUMSS strand with a total of 39 of the frequency counts. It was then followed by the TVL-ICT strand, TVL-HE strand, and ABM strand. Moreover, the majority of the respondents came from a nuclear family with a 178 frequency count, while the lowest frequency count is the stepfamily with a frequency count of 13.

Instruments

This research adapted the questionnaire from a study entitled "Gender Equity Perceptions Among School-Going Adolescents: A Mixed-Methods Comparison Amongst Tribal and Non-Tribal Rural Areas of an Eastern State in India" (Lahiri & Jha, 2022) and another study with the topic of gender role entitled "Determining the Attitudes of University Students Towards Gender Roles" which was first originally from Zeyneloglu and Terzioglu (2008) that was adapted by Sacan et al. (2015) with a few revisions. Additionally, the variables taken from these research tools are all about the attitudes and perceptions of students on gender equity and roles. The profiles needed from the respondents were their gender, strand, and family type. The concept of including gender for the profile variable of gender was taken from the researchers. To determine the students' family type, the researchers decided to include family type as a profile variable in the demographic profile, which can be a nuclear family, single-parent family, extended family, stepfamily, or grandparent family. Moreover, aside from comparing the respondents' family types according to their profile, this study aimed to determine whether family types positively or negatively influence the student's attitudes toward gender roles that can affect their perception of gender equity.

The research tool utilized a survey divided into three parts. For part one, the demographic profile of the respondents was required through identification. In the next part, statements about gender equity, in various categories, and gender roles were given for the respondents to be assessed, mainly using the Likert Scale. For the third and last part, the respondents were asked to give answers to one open-ended question.

The four-point Likert scale determined the respondents' level of perception of gender equity and their attitude toward gender roles, through the statements that were given for them to assess. Researchers calculated their mean to determine whether they were good, average, or poor in their perception of gender equity and their attitude toward gender roles.

This study made use of the Likert Scale, to measure the respondents' perception of gender equity and their attitude toward gender roles, through the statements that were given for them to assess. The respondents answered quantitative questions by marking the numbers (1, 2, 3, or 4) corresponding to their responses, wherein (1) means strongly disagree, (2) means disagree, (3) means agree, and (4) means strongly agree. In addition, researchers assessed the data gathered from the Likert Scale through the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences or SPSS.

Table 2. Cronbach's Alpha Result

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.831	.836	40

Using the SPSS and Cronbach's Alpha where $a > 0.9$ means excellent, $0.9 > a > 0.8$ means good, $0.8 > a > 0.7$ means acceptable, $0.7 > a > 0.6$ means questionable, and $0.6 > a > 0.5$ means poor. The results of the reliability and validity of the instrument used in this study for Cronbach's Alpha and for Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items are 0.831 and 0.836, respectively, which means this study's reliability and validity are good.

Procedure

This study was conducted during the school year 2023- 2024 at Saint Mary's University. The researchers first adapted the research instrument "Gender Equity Perceptions Among School-Going Adolescents: A Mixed-Methods Comparison Amongst Tribal and Non-Tribal Rural Areas of an Eastern State in India" as well as the instrument of the study called "Determining the Attitudes of University Students Towards Gender Roles."

After adapting the instruments from the two studies, the researchers then sought validation of the questionnaire from their research advisor, mentor, and experts. Following that, the researchers secured the approval of the Senior High School Principal to float the questionnaire to their chosen respondents. Then the researchers distributed the questionnaire to the respondents for pilot testing and reliability testing.

Furthermore, tabulation and interpretation of data using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences or SPSS was done after the distribution of questionnaires was done after finishing the distribution of questionnaires. Lastly, presenting and concluding the results were done.

Data Treatment

To analyze the gathered data, the researchers have followed the following statistical tools for the treatment of data:

1. For descriptive statistics, the researchers used frequency and percentage to determine the profile variable of the respondents. The perception of the respondents on gender equity and their attitudes towards gender roles, mean and standard deviation were used. The Likert scale interpretation for attitudes and perception is shown below:

Table 3. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Perception*

<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Description</i>
3.50-4.00	Highly Negative
2.50-3.49	Negative
1.50-2.49	Positive
1.00-1.49	Highly Positive

Table 4. *Likert Scale Interpretation for Attitude*

<i>Mean Score</i>	<i>Description</i>
3.50-4.00	Highly Positive
2.50-3.49	Positive
1.50-2.49	Negative
1.00-1.49	Highly Negative

2. For inferential statistics, to determine whether there is a significant difference between the respondents' perception of gender equity and their attitudes toward gender roles when grouped according to gender, strand, and family type, ANOVA (Analysis of Variance) was used. The researchers also used Pearson's r Correlation, to determine if there is a significant relationship on the perception of the respondents on gender equity towards their attitudes toward gender roles.

3. For the treatment of the Qualitative data, which is the open-ended question of the researchers' instrument, Thematic Analysis was used.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and discussion in the gathered data and its discussion, on the Perception of Senior High School on Gender Equity and their Attitudes toward Gender Roles. This chapter also analyzes the significant difference in the respondent's attitudes toward gender roles and perception of gender equity and the significant relationship. Lastly, this Chapter shows the results on the ways to promote Gender Equity at Saint Mary's University Senior High School given by the respondents.

Section 1: Perception of Gender Equity

Table 5. *Perception of Senior High School Students on Gender Equity*

<i>Statements</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Sd</i>	<i>Qd</i>
1. Once a woman gets married, she belongs to her husband's family	290	2.1414	.97584	Positive Perception
2. A woman should always obey her husband	290	1.8000	.74499	Positive Perception
3. The husband should decide to buy the major household items	290	1.9621	.81632	Positive Perception
4. Boys should be fed before girls during meals	290	1.4655	.63941	Highly Positive Perception
5. Boys should go to school over girls	290	1.4448	.70984	High Positive Perception
6. Boys should get health services over girls	290	1.4483	.71978	Highly Positive Perception
7. Since girls have to get married, they should not be sent for higher education	290	1.3621	.63623	Highly Positive Perception

8. Only boys can perform regular physical activity/work	290	1.4276	.66285	Highly Positive Perception
9. A woman can only take care of her home, kids and cook for her family	290	1.5793	.78188	Positive Perception
10. There are times when a husband or a boy needs to beat his wife or girlfriend	290	1.2862	.63148	Highly Positive Perception
11. A man should have the final word in his home and family members	290	1.6759	.89507	Positive Perception
12. It is necessary to give dowry	290	1.8207	.84156	Positive Perception
13. Only men should work outside the home to sustain the family	290	1.5724	.77366	Positive Perception
14. A woman should tolerate violence in order to keep her family together	290	1.3655	.74233	Highly Positive Perception
15. A man using violence against his wife is a private matter that should not be discussed outside the couple	290	1.4621	.77165	Highly Positive Perception
TOTAL	290	1.58737	.54339	Positive Perception

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Negative Perception), 1.50 – 2.49 (Negative Perception), 2.50 – 3.49 (Positive Perception), 3.50 – 4.00 (Very Positive Perception)

Table 5 shows the perception of Senior High School students on gender equity. According to the table, the calculated sample mean and standard deviation of (M= 1.58737, SD= .54339), and comparing it to the Likert Scale for interpretation, this is in the Positive Level of Perception. Thus, it is clear that SMUSHS students have a positive perception of gender equity which is caused by the respondents being positive in ensuring opportunities and are not limited based on gender because they have more open and accepting ideas for addressing gender disparities or discrimination in a school setting.

To support this result, the study of Lahiri & Jha, (2022) showed a better or positive perception regarding gender equity, may it be about privilege of independence among genders, fairness in decision roles, and especially in financial decision roles. In general, the respondents perceived favorably against gender dominance.

Additionally, a study by Orfan & Samady (2023) resulted to the students’ positive perception of gender equity making them believe in equal education opportunities, equal job opportunities, all sex and genders should have equal access to social services, and equal political to all men and women as well as other gender identities.

Section 2. Attitude on Gender Roles

Table 6. *The Attitude of Senior High School Students towards Gender Roles*

Statements	N	Mean	Sd	Qd
1. At home, whatever the man says should be done.	290	1.5517	.67512	Negative Attitude
2. The occupations of women should be separate from the occupations of men.	290	1.7931	.83103	Negative Attitude
3. The father should have the final say in a young girl’s choice of the person she will marry.	290	1.6621	.89768	Negative Attitude
4. If a woman gives birth to a boy, this increases her value.	290	1.5931	.79789	Negative Attitude
5. Men should be preferred in job applications because of women’s fertility.	290	1.7034	.85344	Negative Attitude
6. Decisions about a woman’s life should be decided by her husband.	290	1.3759	.69110	Highly Negative Attitude
7. Women should prefer keeping silent rather than discussing in the cases that they conflict with their husbands.	290	1.4394	.74347	Highly Negative Attitude
8. A young girl should follow her fathers advises until she gets married.	290	1.9655	1.00458	Negative Attitude
9. A man’s cheating on his wife should be regarded as normal.	290	1.2241	.58950	Highly Negative Attitude
10. If a woman cannot have a baby, the man should marry again.	290	1.2724	.58670	Highly Negative Attitude
11. The basic duty of the women is motherhood.	290	1.9586	1.04815	Negative Attitude
12. Man is the head of the house.	290	2.0069	1.03901	Negative Attitude
13. The most important duty of the man is to earn a living for his family.	290	2.6034	1.11826	Positive Attitude
TOTAL	290	1.703978	.61912	Negative Perception

Legend: 1.00 – 1.49 (Very Negative Attitude), 1.50 – 2.49 (Negative Attitude), 2.50 – 3.49 (Positive Attitude), 3.50 – 4.00 (Very Positive Attitude)

Table 6 presents the attitudes of the respondents towards gender roles. The summarized attitude of 290 respondents shows that they have a negative attitude toward gender roles (x= 1.703978, SD= .61912). This assumes that SMUSHS Students do not agree on the concept of gender roles, this may be because of certain gender roles pushed upon students who identify themselves of another gender rather than acting upon the traditional gender roles. Wherein it is portrayed that men are the heads of the household and occupants of the public, while women have to be housewives, to care for their husbands and children, and to respect privacy (Blackstone, 2017).

To support these results, a study by Sani & Quaranta (2017) revealed that adolescents in different contexts are influenced by the dominant societal discourse on gender inequality, which they interiorize and display through their own attitudes being negative toward gender roles. However, the findings also indicate that young women are more responsive to external cues than young men are.

Along with this is the study of ÇİMEN & SERİN (2021) found that the attitude toward gender roles subscales and meaning orientations were shown to have a statistically positive meaningful association. The explanatory perception of the deserving preference of university students towards “traditional gender role” is very strong.

Section 3. Comparison of the Respondents' Perception of Gender Equity based on their Profile

Table 7. Comparison of the Respondents' Perception of Gender Equity when grouped according to their Gender

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perception of Gender Equity	Female	159	1.5325	.47473	4.685	.000
	Male	79	1.811	.62263		
	Bisexual	27	1.3432	.42915		
	Pansexual	10	1.3867	.40466		
	Gay	8	1.8167	.83171		
	Lesbian	5	1.1867	.20763		
	Non-binary	2	1.5000	.70711		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 7 shows the respondent’s perception on gender equity when grouped according to gender. The analysis revealed a significant difference [F (6, 283) = 4.685, p=.000]. Male respondents exhibited a more positive attitude toward gender equity compared to female respondents, while bisexual and pansexual individuals displayed a more positive perception. Notably, there were no substantial differences in perception between male and

non-binary individuals. This implies that a person’s gender identity can establish a form of perception about the promotion of gender equity and how they want to promote Gender Equity. These findings suggest that gender plays a crucial role in shaping perceptions of gender equity, and this has significant implications for designing targeted interventions and policies aimed at promoting equality.

Similarly, a study by Gonzales et al., (2019) has reported a significant difference between male and female perceptions of their department's treatment and commitment to gender equality, with males generally having a more positive perception.

Table 8. Comparison of the Respondents' Perception of Gender Equity when grouped according to their Strand.

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perception of Gender Equity	STEM	164	1.5496	.49615	4.685	.006
	HUMSS	39	1.6291	.62591		
	TVL-ICT	26	1.5026	.68928		
	AD	21	1.3778	.37555		
	TVL-HE	20	1.9333	.58279		
	ABM	20	1.8033	.48291		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 8 shows the respondents’ perception on gender equity when grouped according to Strand. The result shows that there is a significant difference in the respondents’ perception of gender equity when they are grouped according to their strand

[F (5, 284) = 3.339, p= .006]. This suggests that the perception of students on Gender Equity can differ when they are grouped according to their Strand, where their strand can influence their perception of gender equity. This indicates that this factor can influence how individuals perceive gender equity.

To support this, the result of the study from Kalokoti (2018), the perception of gender equity differs when they are grouped according to various strands. Where the desirable attitude is based on mutual respect and trust between girls and boys.

Table 9. Comparison of the Respondents' Perception of Gender Equity when grouped according to their Family Type.

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Perception of Gender Equity	Nuclear Family	178	1.5760	.53029	2.164	.073
	Single-Parent Family	44	1.5864	.43195		
	Extended Family	37	1.4865	.49712		
	Grand Parent Family	18	1.9296	.75994		
	Stepfamily	13	1.5641	.72501		

*Significant (p<0.05)

Table 9 shows the respondents’ perception on gender equity when grouped according to their profile variables. Results show that there is no significant difference in the perception of gender equity when students are grouped according to their family type [F (4, 285) = 2.164, p= .073]. The result shows that the perception of the students towards gender equity is not connected with their Family Type. This may imply that the respondents’ perception is not rooted in the ideals or beliefs of the family household on gender equity or Gender as a totality.

In another study by Lahiri & Jha, (2022) notable differences in perceptions regarding decision roles and family sustainability were identified among girls, and these differences were found to be statistically significant. Specifically, girls from tribal areas exhibited

higher scores in these domains compared to their counterparts from non-tribal areas.

Section 4. The significant difference in Attitude towards Gender Roles

Table 10. Comparison of the Respondents' Attitude towards Gender Roles, when grouped according to Gender

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Attitude Towards Gender Roles	Female	159	1.6657	.55796	6.354	.000
	Male	79	1.9718	.67005		
	Bisexual	27	1.3390	.43476		
	Pansexual	10	1.2231	.35612		
	Gay	8	1.9327	.93349		
	Lesbian	5	1.2769	.35501		
	Non-binary	2	1.6154	.87029		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 10 shows the results of ANOVA conducted to estimate whether there is a significant difference in the attitude of the respondents towards gender roles based on their gender [$F(6, 283) = 6.354, p = .000$]. To sum up, there exists a significant difference between Male and Female, Male and Bisexual, and Male and Pansexual, resulting in the conclusion that the remaining groups within the gender have no significant difference. This result may imply that dynamics may not be significant in this context because some may cause how the parents set roles with their children. Supporting this result is the study by Hajnalka (2014), which shows that when the respondents are grouped according to their Gender, the respondents have a significant difference in a traditional gender role attitude. In another study by Kharouf and Daoud (2019), The results show that there is a significant difference in the attitudes toward gender roles, where female youth have an attitude towards gender roles that are nontraditional in comparison to those of their male counterparts.

Table 11. Comparison of the Respondents' Attitude towards Gender Roles, when grouped according to Strand

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Attitude on Gender Roles	STEM	164	1.6637	.58784	4.626	.000
	HUMSS	39	1.7022	.66505		
	TVL-ICT	26	1.5621	.76577		
	AD	21	1.4799	.43029		
	TVL-HE	20	2.2269	.50317		
	ABM	20	1.9308	.56796		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 11 shows the results of ANOVA conducted to estimate whether there is a significant difference in the attitude of the respondents towards gender roles based on their strand [$F(5, 284) = 4.626, p = .000$]. This explains that the attitude of the respondents towards gender roles has a significant difference between TVL-ICT and TVL-HE, HUMSS and TVL-HE, TVL-HE and STEM, AD, and TVL-HE. So, the accompanying null hypothesis is to be rejected, leading to the conclusion that there is a significant difference in their attitude toward gender roles when they are grouped according to their strand. This suggests that a person's strand may influence their attitude toward gender roles, given the variations in curriculums and specialized fields associated with each strand.

To support these results, a study by Monleon and Balsomo (2023), that the findings of their study revealed that there is a significant difference in learning of gender expression of the students from all the strands. Respondents in Grade 11 and Grade 12. Strands including, HE-TVL Track, HUMSS, GAS, and ICT have shown significant differences.

Table 12. Comparison of the Respondents' Attitude towards Gender Roles, when grouped according to Family Type

Factors	Groups	f	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Attitude on Gender Roles	Nuclear Family	178	1.6979	.59032	2.743	.029
	Single-Parent Family	44	1.7308	.57168		
	Extended Family	37	1.5199	.60241		
	Grand Parent Family	18	2.0983	.72919		
	Stepfamily	13	1.6686	.85795		

*Significant ($p < 0.05$)

Table 12 shows the results of ANOVA conducted to estimate whether there is a significant difference in the attitude of the respondents towards gender roles based on their family type [$F(4, 285) = 2.743, p = .029$]. As a result, there exists a significant difference between respondents whose family type is Extended Families and Grandparent Families, leading to the conclusion that the remaining groups within the family type have no significant difference. This may imply that certain family types can influence one's attitude toward Gender Roles, as the household imposes different beliefs and ideals on the students.

According to Halimi et al. (2016), there is a significant difference in attitude toward gender roles when group according to family type. But only shows a significant difference in the single-parent, nuclear, and extended family types.

Section 5. The Significant relationship in the perception of Gender Equity on the Respondents' Attitude Towards Gender Role

Table 13. Significant Relationship on the Perception of Saint Mary’s University Senior High School in Gender Equity and their Attitude in Gender Roles

Indicator	Pearson r	P-value (sig)	QD
Perception of gender equity ↔ Attitude toward gender roles	.838**	.000	Very High Correlation

Table 13 shows the Correlation between the perception of Senior High School Students in their perception of Gender Equity and their Attitude Towards Gender Roles. it shows that there is a significant relationship between both variables, with the negative attitude toward Gender roles and the Senior High School Students’ positive perception of Gender Equity, with a Pearson r of .838** and sig. (2-tailed) of .000, there exists a High Positive Correlation. This result may imply that if there is a negative attitude toward gender roles, their perception of gender equity is positively correlated with each other as they reject the idea of gender roles being implemented to restrict a student’s way of expressing their selves.

Similar to the results of the correlation in the perception of gender equity and their attitude towards gender roles of Senior High School Students, a study by Bențea and Anghelache (2012), shows that there is a correlation between the different teachers’ perceptions of their professional activity and the differences in the levels of job satisfaction depending on the perception of the teaching profession in work.

Section 6. Qualitative Analysis

Table 14. Recommendations of the respondents in the promotion of Gender Equity

Recommendations	Response	Frequency	Percentage
Respect all genders and stop various forms of bullying	My recommendations on the promotion of Gender Equity are people should respect and treat everyone equally. Treating each other with respect not belittling one gender over another, because everyone has the right to whatever they want. Do not bully and respect who they are. Treat anyone with respect without bias. We should respect each gender and don’t speak ill about them. But respect doesn’t mean tolerating any wrongdoing that could affect other people.	147	50.6
Create Forums, seminars, and online promotion to educate students	I should or would say, have seminars to be respectful to others despite of their Sexuality. Cause if we keep fighting for acceptance, if there’s no respect then it’s useless. Engage in programs promoting Gender Equity to the betterment of our society. My recommendations in the promotion of Gender Equity are having a seminars or program where gender equity is promote awareness. 4) There should be a time where the school will create a program or activity about gender equality. Policies may also help to further promote gender equality.	64	22.1
Let the school be Inclusive, not Exclusive	1) We should always be equal in terms of gender and girls/women should be treated equally and not by discriminating them in terms of gender. 2) Give all gender same opportunities 3) Avoid segregating boys and girls into separate lines, separate sports activities and mix seating up in the classroom. Being exclusive at school. Have different orientations for knowledge or further knowledge. Have strict consequences for those who discriminate.	46	15.9
Equalities(Gender Free) Activities	1) Equalize activities between men and women 2) the one that I would like to recommend is that the school make an event for LGBTQ Like Some kind of competition for an entertaining event 3) Allowing students to participate in activities regardless of their gender. Allowing and encouraging	17	5.9

		them to speak their minds while also being mindful of the feelings of other students.		
Creation of organization	and	1) Club for gender equity	10	3.4
Infrastructure and provide service to various gender	to promote equity	2) Offer another set of CRs for the third gender. Being gender inclusive, such as promoting the inclusion of all genders in different categories in sports and other social activities.		
Creation of discrimination	policies free from	1.) The school should be implementing or applying gender equity 2.) Remove the dress code and haircut policy. 3.) Make strict rules that would prevent discrimination for all genders. Teach also to student that gender role is not the basis of one's value.	6	2.1
Total			290	100

Table 14 shows the qualitative analysis of this research, using the thematic analysis of the recommendations of the respondents to promote Gender Equity in Saint Mary's University Senior High School. The majority of the recommendations that the respondents' answered were, Respecting all genders without bias with a frequency of 60. Followed by establishing forums or programs to promote the concepts and ideals of gender equity, while 35 respondents answered that the school becomes an inclusive institution and not an exclusive one. Another is to implement the study of equity and equality in the school curriculum, in order to educate students on the importance of gender equity. The least recommendations of the respondents were; to remove gender roles and stereotypes in the school, promote freedom of expression, and inclusivity in the school, Equalized activities in the school, online promotion like posters and video promotion to spread awareness, and creation of an inclusive organization on gender equity and infrastructures that caters to various Genders.

The study by Domínguez et al. (2019), that evidence suggests that the important positive benefits associated with attending schools that have anti-bullying or inclusive policies for gender minorities, such as the improvement of school well-being, a more positive school climate, lowering the levels of victimization, and decreasing school harassment, are the keys to ensure the security and the sense of safety for every student.

According to the study by Klemmer et al. (2019), School absences can be due to safety concerns as well as bullying, which are common among other genders. It has stated that socially assigned gender non-conforming adolescents, regardless of sexual orientation or gender identity, are at greater risk of missing school due to safety concerns, and bullying, as compared with those who conform to norms of gender expression.

Conclusion

This study explores the perceptions and attitudes regarding gender equity among Grade 11 and 12 students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School, involving 290 participants. Notably, respondents from SMU SHS express a positive stance on gender equity, rejecting traditional roles and advocating for equal opportunities irrespective of gender. Interestingly, variations based on gender, sexual orientation, and academic strands were observed, emphasizing the need for tailored interventions in educational settings. Additionally, the strong correlation between supporting gender equity and opposing traditional gender roles underscores the importance of fostering awareness and dismantling stereotypes to create a more inclusive educational environment.

The implications of these findings extend to the broader educational landscape, emphasizing the necessity for institutions to actively promote gender equity, challenge stereotypes, and address the diverse perspectives and experiences of students. By recognizing the influence of academic paths and family backgrounds on attitudes, educational initiatives can be tailored to foster a more inclusive and equitable learning environment. This study provides valuable insights for policymakers and educators seeking to implement effective strategies that address the complex interplay of factors shaping students' perceptions of gender equity and roles.

With consideration of the results and conclusions, the researchers have made recommendations on the promotion of gender equity in schools. These recommendations were considered and advised by the researchers as their basis to address the gender-based discrimination present in school, and in the exploration of how the students perceive and understand gender equity. Also, recommendations were also directed toward the school administration and other researchers for the possible continuity or future studies of similar topics such as Gender Equity and Gender Roles.

It is highly recommended to the school that to maintain the respondents' positive perception of gender equity, online advocacies and campaigns showing and making the senior high school students understand and apply the concept of being fair and unbiased through the help of using the school's official hashtag will ensure that opportunities are not limited based on gender for the reason that students

will be more open and will continue to accept ideas to address gender bias or discrimination present in a school setting. To promote the reality that gender roles perpetuate inequality and are harmful to society, it is highly recommended that everyone avoid feeling oppressed by this topic. Speaking out inside the campus when we notice discrimination is one way to begin with because it helps those who are being discriminated against.

Additionally, the recommendation for the school's administration is to support campaigns, or rather, starting campaigns wherein we share these ideas is a great way to help but one of the most important aspects of overcoming gender roles is education.

Implementing equalized (gender-free) activities for the students. People should start by understanding that gender roles promote the concept of gender inequality. Every individual on our campus should accept the fact that all genders are all equal.

Educating every student about having a positive perception of gender equity influences their negative attitude towards gender roles through seminars or symposiums is highly recommended to maintain the high positive correlation between both variables because, in that way, every individual will be open enough to accept and understand both variables that are mentioned. Simply accepting facts about these variables and respecting every individual without discrimination, regardless of gender, could make our campus free from gender biases and gender discrimination.

The primary objective of this study is to address gender inequality in school and in order to achieve it, future researchers should have a larger number of respondents with at least half of the total population of the target respondents. To add, the research respondents should also include the whole senior high school staff and employees and not the senior high school students only. Furthermore, adding religion as a profile variable is recommended to determine if the respondents' religious sector influences their ideas and opinion of gender equity and gender roles, and if there may be a significant difference in their attitude toward gender roles. Additionally, it is also recommended to have an equal distribution of the questionnaires to groups of various genders, extending it not only to senior high school students but to college students as well. After all, it is also highly recommended to implement a form of advertisement about the awareness of the students through posting online, with the help of Marialis Pons, that gender roles are not a positive thing, rather it restricts various forms of gender. Lastly, for future studies similar to this study, it is highly recommended to include, make a basis, and consider local issues that are present in our country or simply put, Filipino context issues and studies to support the major concepts and topics.

With all the recommendations gathered in this study, respecting all genders and stopping various forms of bullying is our number one goal, followed by educating each individual through forums that will give awareness to them. Moreover, it is also recommended that the school stop being exclusive and be inclusive instead, which will eventually lead to the elimination of gender roles and stereotypes present on our campus. Having to promote freedom of expression on our campus is also highly recommended, this promotion can be in the form of activities that are gender-free with the use of promotional materials to provide awareness and information about gender equity. Furthermore, the creation of organizations and infrastructures that would promote equity which will lead to equality and provide services to various genders is highly recommended.

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